

Early Chola's Shiva temple of Vedal and Dravidian Architecture

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ABSTRACT

Five kilo meters west of the East Coast Road in Chengalpattu District, Chittamur Union, Seyyur Circle, lies the beautiful village of Vedal. There is a Shiva temple here. The base of the Shiva temple here looks like a model structure built in stone during the Pallavar period. The Vedal Shiva Temple is majestic with features of early Chola and Dravidian architecture. The temple was built by Rajaraja Chola and maintained by Rajendra Chola. The special feature of this temple is Vimana. The vimana of the temple is built of bricks. Vedal Shiva Temple is built following all aspects of Dravidian architecture. This temple is built following the design of Dhongana Mata temple. In Thondai Mandal, when the Pallavas ruled, the temple designed and built by them is the Tungani Matakcoil structure. These are the method of temple construction followed from the Sangam period. Corresponding literary evidence for this is to be found in the Sangam literature. Dravidian architecture is an art developed by the Pallavas and cultivated by the Cholas. The evolution of Dravidian architecture was followed by the Vijayanagara kings and Nayaks and reached a high level. The layout of temples built in India especially in Tamil Nadu was different from the layout of temples built in other regions. Historians call this style an evolution of Dravidian architecture. Dhonganai Matak Temple is found in Thondai Mandal, Pallavaram, Trishulam, Tiruvettiur etc. The construction structure of Thuganani Matak Koil is also found in areas like Thirukkalugunram. The purpose of this article is to describe the architectural special features of the Dormanai Matakkoivil of the Shiva Temple located at Vedal.

Key words: Vedal – Pallavas – Rajaraja Cholan – Shiva Temple – Dravidian Architecture – Dhongana Matak Temple – Four Pillared Artha Mandapam.

Introduction:

Vedal is a town located on the east coast in Seiyur Circle of Chengalpattu District. Located on the east coast, four kilometers from Kadappakkam, Vedal is situated in the western direction. It is a small town located at a distance of 100 km from Chennai and 50 km from Pondicherry. Vedal has a lot of history. During Sangam period the Vedal was a part of the Thondai Nadu and was the gateway to the South Tamil country. Vedal is a separate state in Ethur region. Vedal is located near the village of Nallur Nattathanar, who lived in the country of Edaikazhi, and the poet of the Sangha period, who wrote Sirupanartuppa. The most important historical attraction is the dome-shaped Shiva temple in Vedal. The name of the Shiva temple located in Vedal is Thiruvathavamuganeshuvarar. An ancient Shiva temple located at Vedal is a foundation of Pallava period architectural features. The foundation of this temple is made of black stone. The unique feature of Vedal is the Shiva temple built in the form of a sleeping loft and with Chola architecture. Among the temple architecture described in the Sangam literature, the Dhonganai Matak temple is unique. The purpose of this paper is to describe the special features of the architecture of Dhonganaimadak Temple at Vedal.

Architecture not just about building.

Architecture is one of the most important forms in which the culture of any people has found expression. Temple architecture in Tamil Nadu is largely theocentric. According to Diebedo Francis Kere in Washington post, Architecture is not just about building. It's a means of improving people's quality of life. The term "Architecture" is derived from the Latin word architectura, meaning the leading worker or a skilled artisan or craftsman, it is an art blending to technical skill, imagination and beauty. Architecture is the scientific knowledge of people. It reflects in many ways the life style, religious, economic and social activities of people.

"Temples are great institutions

"Temples were the only art space. These ancient architecture are marvellous. Temples were not merely places of worship. They were a record of our history, tradition and literature. The vast information available in inscriptions on temple walls."¹ "Temples are great institutions and they have traditionally been central to everyone's life. It is not only a place of

worship, but also integral to the socio, cultural and economic life of people. “With its rich granaries, the temple helped to feed the hungry. The temple very often played the role of a Court of Law for settling disputes.”

“Temples being the centre of all activities playing a major role during the Chola period became an insignificant institution with their decline is also referred.”² Details of temples and its documentations has been collected and systematically arranged based on five important factors. Literatures are the starting point for the etymology of the place and then the architecture and the different dynasties that have added many layers to the spaces. Epigraphy and literature associated with the temple and festivals are also crucial to the research scholars.”³

Different Names of temple in Sangam Age.

The Sangam and post Sangam literature beginning from 2nd century B.C to the 6th century A.D speaks of the temples are **Kottam, Nagaram, Koil, Palli and Peedikai** dedicated to different deities. **The Agananuru** one of the earliest works of Sangam literature describes a banyan tree in worship as surrounded by a brick enclosure and to which offerings were made.it also refers to the ruins of a temple built of bricks (poem 167). **The Purananuru** another Sangam work refers to a temple of Siva (Poem 6). According to Pattinappalai, Karikala, the great Chola King is said to have erected temples to Gods, while building the city of Uraiyur for settling hid subjects (Lines 283-287)

The advent of Nayanmars of Saivism and Alwars of Vaishnavism gave a new life and energy to the temple worship in south India. They travelled length and breadth of the country and sanctified hundreds of temples in the south by their sacred songs. There are 274 Saivite temples which are mentioned in “Thevaram” and “Tiruvasakam” and there are 108 Vishnu Temple.”⁴

The plinth of the Vedal temple - a specimen of Pallavar architecture.

The plinth of the Shiva temple at Vedal is built following the construction of the Pallavar period...the plinth of the black stone sanctum is still visible today. The plinth of the Shiva temple is similar to the plinth of the Pallava kings. Like the plinth of the Shiva temple found at Vedal, the structure of the Shiva temple located at Vayalur near Parameswaram is similar. And the Dhonganai Matak temple in Thirukkalukunram is similar.

Vedal Shiva temple during Chola period

Vedal Shiva temple was built during Rajaraja Chola I period. Reconstruction was done during Rajendra's time. Historical records show that maintenance works were carried out during the reign of Parakesarivarman, a later Chola. During the reign of Rajaraja Chola, Uma Pattaki, the wife of the Khon of the middle land, who was the king of Kurunila, erected idols of Kuthaphiran and made it possible for the worship to continue, and the news that donations were given to light the Nanda lamp in the Palliyarai room is recorded in the inscriptions here. And the awards of Rajendra Chola and the Meikeertis of Rajaraja Chola are found in the inscription in this temple. Along with it there is an inscription carved during the reign of Rajendra I.”⁵

Sangam Temples

“During the Sangam period, the palaces, temples and mandapas were built by scholars who studied sculpture, looked at the day, looked at the calendar, measured with straight hands in the right direction, worshiped and worshiped the deities in the figs, and the temples were planned and planned properly.

Temple system

All the temple building methods of Tamils are based on the Tamil Agamas. Thirumoolar, who wrote the Agamas in Tamil, mentions the names of the nine Agamas he wrote. In the Dharmathu Pāl in the Agama, he first mentions the name of the Agama as the cause. About the structures of the temple, the Agama Prasana gives us many new explanations. In the past, the temples built by the Tamils were built with the emphasis on the sanctum sanctorum only. In course of time Artha Mandapam was built. If we examine the temple structures of Tamil Nadu, it is well known that the Tamils had a sophisticated mathematical knowledge of geometry thousands of years ago.

The Karuvarai (The sanctum sanctorum- Akanazhigai - Karpagaram)

The sanctum sanctorum (the womb) is the main part of the temple. In earlier times, the Tamil people used to call the sanctum sanctorum as a temple. This womb is also called Moolathanam (Mulasthanam). This is where God is. That means there will be Shiva Lingam. At the highest point of every temple is the image of the God in the sanctum sanctorum. The

gate tower is revered as the foot and the sanctum as the head. The Tamils call the temple as Akanazhigai, Nyazhigai, Karuvarai (Carppagragam) Thiruvarai, St. Vernaculars call it Garbhagraha. The sanctum sanctorum of the Shiva temple at Vedal is built following the circular measurement system.”⁶

Dravidian Vimanam (Shikhara)

“The site of the temple is located on the high hill of the village and have a large natural water body towards the north and a manmade square temple tank to the east .The main temple with Dravidian Shikhara is dedicated to Shiva and have a four pillared square hall and a semi-circular sanctum with Shiva linga. The hall has a flat roof and the sanctum or Garbha Graha has a high Shikhara. The temple and the shrines are mainly built of bricks with stone used for the foundation and parts of the superstructure.”⁷

Two ancillary shrines.

There are two other ancillary shrines in the temple complex.one called Ganesha Mandapa and other one goddess (Devi) shrines are there. Sculptures of the Dwarapala, Grama Devi and Devts are also there.

Elephant back style of architecture

The temple is more ancient than 994 AD per Archaeological finding and is a Treasure trove for the history. ”The temple is a”Thoonganai Madam temple with Gajaprashta vimaanam.”⁸”It is more difficult to incorporate the elephant back in brick than in stone. Thus the present temple is a very rare specimen representing great artistic skill. The temple possess inscriptions on parts of the structure. Thus stylistically the temple May belong to early Cholas period. (Eighth-ninth century A.D)

The shrines are mainly built of bricks with stone used for the foundation and parts of the superstructure. The main shrine is in Gajaprishta (elephant back) style of architecture. The earliest Temple, representing such an architectural style, is the Nakula- Sakadeva Ratha of Mahabalipuram (mid-seventh century) later, up to around the ninth century, many temples of this style were built in Pallavaram tirsoolam area.

The main shrine of the Adhipureswarar temple of Tiruvettriur is also of the same style but all these Gajaprishta style Temple except the present Temple at Vedal are made of stone. Thus the temple at Vedal is a rare specimen of a brick-built Gajaprishta temple.”⁹

Vimanam

Vimana means the stupa built over the sanctum and the meaning is stated. Vimana is described in the sculptural centuries as well-measured. The Agamas are the hundred authoritative descriptions of the planes. Tirumantram is the book which is revered as the Tamil Agama. It has been said that 'Pure Vimana is also dust' 1289. The explanation for this is the raised, covered area above the womb.

Vimanam means well-measured. In temples, the sanctum sanctorum houses the image of the deity. A high plane will be erected on it. When the people coming from the distant towns see the plane, the worshiper thinks that they have seen the image of the Lord. In earlier times Vimana was the highest part of the temple. Gate towers are not built high. It is not a Tamil tradition to worship the image of the Lord by seeing the tower. That is not the case either. It is said that Vimana was in Tamil Nadu, having structures ranging from one level to 14 levels. The Sangha books give evidence that the palaces in Tamil Nadu also had seven levels. Images of many deities were installed in the planes that arose in Tamil Nadu later on.”¹⁰

Vimanam in Tamil Nadu

Until the reign of the Pallava king Narasimhavarman I (630 to 660 AD), Mamallapuram had only model temples carved out of single stone. According to sculptors, the first stone temple carved with planes in Tamil Nadu was the Mahabalipuram cave temple carved by the Pallava king. Some people believe that the temples in Tamil Nadu were built with Vimanams on the model of these temples. This opinion is contrary to the data in the books like Pathupattu, Silapathikaram, Manimekalai, Perumpanathrupa, Nedunal Vadai etc. which we have highlighted earlier. Appar and Tirunanasambandar who lived in the beginning of the sixth century AD also went to the temples like Chidambaram, Sirkazhi, Pennadagam, Madurai, Tirunelveli, Vaigal, Tirupathirip Puliyur etc. temples, Karakoil, Njahalkoil, Kokutik Koil, Dhongana Mata Koil, Ilangkoil, Manikoil, Matakkoil etc. Literary evidence confirms

the worship of deities. It cannot be denied that the Chola king Kochengannan in the fourth century AD built 70 roof temples and the songs sung by Sammandar and Thirumangai Alvar.

There is no doubt that the temples, gopurams and vimanas built by Mahendravarman and Paramesvaravarman and their successors at Mamallapuram and Kanchipuram were the temples followed by the ancient Tamils. The system of erecting temples, towers and vimanas existed before the arrival of Christians in Tamil Nadu. The Pallavas started building Karungoils in Tamil Nadu following Tamil architecture and Tamil religious worship. They were guided by the Agamas found by the Tamils, books on sculpture and the works of sculptors of Tamil Nadu.

After the Tamils built more temples made of bricks and mortar during the Sangam period, after that it became a black stone gopuram and a temple. Our architectural history tells us that they evolved into airplanes. Even in this period, there are towers and vimanas with multi-colored images of Buddha in Tamil Nadu. The custom of beautifully designing gopurams like domes is a noble practice followed by the Dravidians.

The special part of the temple is the sanctum sanctorum. Another highlight is the aircraft built on top of it. The upper platform built over the gate leading to the interior of the wall is called a gopuram. Whatever the meaning of this, the sight of the vimana built on the sanctum sanctorum is considered as seeing the deity within, and people come from afar and worship the vimana as if they saw the image of the Lord.”¹¹

Dhongana Mata Temple

The opposite side is like a wooden floor and the back two corners are set up like an elephant's back.”¹²

Dhonganai Mata Temples in Tamil Nadu

In Tamil Nadu, Thuganani Mata temples are semi-circular temples. We are not going to explore aircraft systems in this chapter. We take only the wombs for examination. The sanctum sanctorum in some Dhongana Mata temples is almost semi-circular in shape. The sanctum sanctorum of the Vadamelaiswarar temple in Oragadam, near Chengalpattu, has a semi-circular structure. In general, all Thomgani Mata Temples can be said to be semi-circular temples. However, some sanctuaries are found to be narrow chambered temples and

some are long semi-circular temples. The temple has a long sanctum sanctorum, a small artha mandapam and a hall. This temple was built in the sixth century. Although there are many semi-circular temples in Kanchipuram district, the structure of this temple amazed the Bengal researcher O.C. Gangoli wrote a rare article about this in his special edition of Roopa, Monday, 30 years ago, drawing a floor plan and a silhouette portrait. It is noteworthy that this Oragadam Vadameswarar temple was also featured in the book Indian Architecture.”¹³

Vedal Dhongana Matak Temple

What is seen here is how the back of a huge yawn can be seen if it is standing, and the back part of the sanctum sanctorum of the temple is built in the shape of a dome. The distinctive feature of the temple is the design of the rear part of the yanai. The structure of vimana above the sanctum sanctorum in Dhonganai Mata temple located at Vedal is also built as a three-tiered vimana. The same structure as in Vedal is also found at Vayalur near Palatu, but there is no vimana.

Halls

Halls are built inside temples. A wide, long common room is set up for weddings to the deities during the festival, swings, evening entertainments, dances, dancing, etc. Outside the temples, the people, kings and merchants have built mandapas to stay here and there on the main streets when the images of the deity come in procession. Literature says that in ancient times there were many halls in the palaces of Tamilnadu kings.

The idols of God are not decorated and worshiped daily in the mandapams set up in the temples. Here the images of the Gods come in procession on wheels and stay for a few hours. Then people will stand there and worship. At other times music concerts, dance concerts and lectures are held in the halls. Outside the temples, people stay in mandapams built by individuals and clans on the streets. In places like Tiruchendur and Madurai, many castes have erected mandapas in the name of their caste. These halls are of two types. One is built with utility in mind. And for God, the sanctum sanctorum was built earlier by the scholar.

The hall in front of the sanctum is the Artha Mandapam. Artha Mandapam has four pillars. The area between Karuvara and Artha Mandapam is called Antaralam. Maha

Mandapam has six pillars. Vedal Shiva temple has sanctum sanctorum, artha mandapam and maha mandapam.”¹⁴

Temple inscriptions

“In the Vadavamukagnisvara temple, on the base of the east wall of the central shrine, inscriptions of Rajaraja Chola I, regnal year of 9, in 994 A.D were found in which gifts of land by kulirkoyil, the wife of.....Eran Sutti alias Pallava idaikkalinattu-kon of which one was for maintaining a perpetual lamp in the palliyarai of the deities kuttapperumal and umabhattalaraki. The latter image was set up by the donatrix herself. The makasaba of Vidal in Vidal-nadu in Indur-kottam probably exempted the lands for taxes. “¹⁵

“In the Vadavamukagnisvara temple, on a stone set up on front of the same temple, inscriptions of Rajaraja Chola I, regnal year of 20, 1032 A.D were found in which tax exemption of lands by the saba was mentioned.

Records a gift of two pieces of land purchased for gold by the Mahasabha of sola kerala Chaturvedimangalam alias Vidal in Vidal Nadu of Indur kottam for maintaining two lamps for the Thiruvadavamukhagnisvaram-Udaiyar of Vidal by Tuttan viratungan alias sola keralapperiyaruayan of Panditachola Chaturvedimangalam alias Munnuru in Oyma Nadu in Jayankonda Cholamandalam.”¹⁶

“In the Rajendra Chola I regnal year of 31, 1043 A.D Records an undertaking given by the Mahasabha of sola kerala Chaturvedimangalam Indur kottam in Jayankonda Cholamandalam to a certain Malaiyakulantaka periyariaian for providing food, offerings and four lamps to Adavallar, a deity in the temple of land donated by him and making the same tax-free for a consideration of 30 panaams.”¹⁷

”Chola-Parakesarivarman regnal year 16, in 11 & 16 the century A.D, on the base of the east wall of the central shrine in the same temple, records a gift of land, purchased from Tirumangalagilan Anunganaraiyan of Vedal in Indur kottam as madappuram to a certain matha for supplying firewood for four months beginning from the month of karttigai and water for four months beginning from the months of panguni by Arangan Namiyandani, the kilan of Velikpakkam in Anangur in Anangurkurram in Panaiyur Nadu.”¹⁸

Inscriptions Regarding Festivals

”In the 11 th century A.D inscriptions,on the pillars in the mandapa in front of the same temple, were found regarding record a grant of land for providing and offerings for conducting festivals on various occasions like Chittiraivishu,Margali Thiruvadira,etc,to the God at vedal.“19

Conclusion

In brief, the temple is not a mere architectural marvel. It is an institution intimately connected with man and his life to lead in rationalist way. Dravidian temples do not follow or follow any national temple structure. Dravidian architecture uses only one orderly system. It is called Dravidian system. Although the review of Dravidian architecture is not yet well done in our country, a proper review of Dravidian architecture in our country should be done. If the Dravidian architectural methods are thoroughly studied at least in one place, if the discipline of Dravidian architecture is scientifically investigated and the truth revealed, the same method will easily spread throughout the country. Then it becomes easier for people in other areas to explore further.

Foot Notes

- 1) The Hindu Newspaper-page 1&4 Justices R.Mahadevan and J.Sathya Narayana Prasath.
- 2) A History of South India by Nilakandasastri, Madras Oxford university press,1976
- 3) Madhusudanan Kalaichelvan-Friday Review Page 2-The Hindu Newspaper – Chennai Friday,November 18,2022
- 4) South Indian Temples – by S.Padmanabhan, Kumaran Pathippagam,20,State Bank Colony,Nagercoil _1
- 5) ARE 1919 Nos 170-173,ARE 1959 Nos 175-185 lbid -1965-66 Nos 712 lbid-1966-67 Nos 190-191
- 6) Tamil Nadu Temple Architecture – Sathankulam R.Ragavan.Abisan Puplication – Chennai-87-Page181-186
- 7) Report on the visit to ancient temple at Vedal village on 15 September, 2014 By- Dr.Divay Gupta- Director of Architectural Heritage Division at INTACH, New Delhi.

- 8) Report on the visit to ancient temple at Vedal village on 23 August,2014 By- Dr. Suresh- Tamil Nadu state convenor for the Indian National Trust for Art and Cultural Heritage (INTACH)
- 9) Tamil Nadu Temple Architecture – Sathankulam R.Ragavan. Abisan Puplication – Chennai-87-Page189
- 10) Tamil Nadu Temple Architecture – Sathankulam R.Ragavan. Abisan Puplication – Chennai-87-Page194
- 11) Tamil Nadu Temple Architecture – Sathankulam R.Ragavan. Abisan Puplication – Chennai-87- Page197
- 12) Tamil Nadu Temple Architecture – Sathankulam R.Ragavan. Abisan Puplication – Chennai-87- Page 214
- 13) Tamil Nadu Temple Architecture – Sathankulam R.Ragavan. Abisan Puplication – Chennai-87- Page 273
- 14) ARE 1961-62:NO.175:TVM p.338
- 15) ARE 1961-62:NO.185:TVM p.338
- 16) ARE 1961-62:NO.179:TVM p.338
- 17) ARE 1961-62:NO.182:TVM p.338
- 18) ARE 1961-62:NO.177 - 179:TVM p.338